

The Global Kinematic Equations

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13 October 2024

Abstract—The *Global Kinematic Equations (GKE)* are defined and explained in this manuscript. This work aims to approach the scalars of speed, acceleration, curvature, and torsion from a *global perspective*, making these definitions more suitable for practical applications, especially in scenarios where noise may render traditional local definitions unusable. Theoretical results are validated through experiments, where an Extended Kalman Filter's estimation of curvature is compared to an estimation derived using the second Global Kinematic Equation. It is demonstrated that the latter performs better in the presence of noise.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gottfried Wilhelm Leibnitz, in 1684 [1] and Isaak Newton, in 1687 [2] (in chronological order), introduced the ideas of infinitesimal calculus as the basis to define instantaneous velocity and acceleration in motion. Today, after 340 years, differentials have been used almost everywhere to describe instantaneous (local) changes and are considered one of the most basic tool for analysis in almost every scientific and professional domain. But they suffer with noise. For tracking motion in particular, technological advancements have converged in the use of radars that measure distances and angles of moving objects and even though these measurements either inherently (interferences) or by purpose (jamming) are highly noisy, differentials dominate calculations behind these systems, lacking as it seems an alternative global model of motion. There have been numerous attempts to resist noise, mainly by using Kalman Filters in various forms, e.g. [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] [9] [10] but the model equations of differential nature, remain loyal to their ancestors of renaissance.

The motivation behind this manuscript is to investigate *global alternatives* to the classical differential definitions of motion and discover advantages these may have in relation to noise. A first candidate for redefinition is *curvature*. Curvature even though a scalar, describes the change of *direction* in motion but is also highly sensitive to noise as a higher order differential. The *Global Kinematic Equations* presented in this manuscript are based on integral of distances to define the *scalars* of speed, acceleration, torsion and curvature in a way that is not dependent directly on the instantaneous change of position but rather on the instantaneous change of an integral of distances that is less affected by noise due to its aggregate nature. Experiments show that examining the changes of aggregate distances rather than the change in position, improves curvature calculations in the presence of noise. Similar concepts regarding curvature have been investigated in [11], [12] and [13] but the concern there was for shape analysis, indexing and retrieval.

II. PRELEMINARIES

Lets consider a motion trajectory $\alpha(t)$ in 3D, parametrized by time t and an arbitrary set of points \mathcal{M} , from where the motion is observed. There is no restriction for \mathcal{M} , it can be either a 2D manifold embedded in 3D (e.g. a sphere), an arbitrary object of any dimension or just a few points here and there. To facilitate extension of this work in the future, a sphere will be used hereinafter. The movement is assumed to happen in 3D space, independent of the sphere. Bold typeface signify vectors or vector functions. α is the trajectory of movement; a vector function from \mathbb{R} into the Euclidian 3D space \mathbb{R}^3 .

α is considered smooth enough to accept differentiation up to the third order (at least three times differentiable). This condition is not restrictive for the usual digital curves (polylines), as any polyline can acquire this property after suitable treatment at its *corners* at an infinitesimal level. It is thus required here because the Mathematics have to make sense as *classic differential geometry* will be used. At time t_* the *sum or integral of distances* between $\alpha(t_*)$ and the arbitrary set of points \mathcal{M} , will be studied here. This entity will be called *total distance*, will be denoted with ϕ and will be defined as the sum of all distances between this point and all points in \mathcal{M} e.g. in the continous case,

$$\phi(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \|\alpha(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\|$$

where the integral is interpreted accordingly, e.g. in the case of a discrete \mathcal{M} it signifies a mechanism of enumerating all points of \mathcal{M} in a summation of their distances to the moving particle, whereas in the continuous case of a sphere it signifies a double integral of its parametric angles. In the general case of a continuous munifold patch, it may signify a double integral on its curvilinear coordinates [14].

The scalars of speed, acceleration, curvature and torsion will be defined through this total distance, a fact that will make them robust to noise and more suitable in practical applications. Lets start by studing the distance between a random point on the path of motion and another random point on the sphere.

As shown if Fig.(1), consider a random point p in \mathcal{M} , a random point in time t_* , the *Frenet-Serret* frame at $\alpha(t_*)$ (also denoted as point O), the vector from p to O denoted by \mathbf{r} , \mathbf{r}' the projection of \mathbf{r} on the *osculating* plane, ω the angle from the normal vector to \mathbf{r}' , measured on the osculating plane *counterclockwise* and θ the angle from the binormal to \mathbf{r} . θ is restricted to $[0, \pi]$ because the length of the projection of \mathbf{r} which equals $\|\mathbf{r}\| \sin(\theta)$ must always be positive. Angles ω and θ are scalars of t and p . \mathbf{r} is a vector

also of t and \mathbf{p} but for the moment lets consider \mathbf{p} fixed on the sphere and treat \mathbf{r} as of a single parameter, that of time. The distance from \mathbf{p} to $\alpha(t_*) \equiv O$ is $\|\mathbf{r}\|$, the length of \mathbf{r}' is $\|\mathbf{r}'\| = \|\mathbf{r}\|\sin(\theta)$ thus

$$\mathbf{r} = \|\mathbf{r}\|(-\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta), \cos(\omega)\sin(\theta), -\cos(\theta)) \quad (1)$$

The Frenet-Serret equations are:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{T}}{ds} = \kappa \mathbf{N} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}}{ds} = -\kappa \mathbf{T} + \tau \mathbf{B} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{B}}{ds} = -\tau \mathbf{N} \quad (4)$$

where s is the *arc length* parameter. Using the Frenet-Serret equations the first *vector derivative* of the position vector can be calculated:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} = \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{ds} \frac{ds}{dt} = \mathbf{T}u = (u(t), 0, 0) \quad (5)$$

where u is the speed, a scalar of t and \mathbf{T} the *tangent vector*. The second derivative of the position vector can also be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\mathbf{r}}{dt^2} &= \frac{d(\mathbf{T}u)}{dt} = u \frac{d\mathbf{T}}{dt} + \frac{du}{dt} \mathbf{T} = u \frac{d\mathbf{T}}{ds} \frac{ds}{dt} + \frac{du}{dt} \mathbf{T} \\ &= \kappa v^2 \mathbf{N} + \gamma \mathbf{T} = \kappa v^2(0, 1, 0) + \gamma(1, 0, 0) = (\gamma, \kappa v^2, 0) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where κ , γ are the curvature and acceleration respectively (scalars of time), \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{N} are the tangent and normal vectors. The resulting vector in Eq.6 is called the *curvature vector*. One can also proceed accordingly for the third derivative of the position vector:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3\mathbf{r}}{dt^3} &= \frac{d(\kappa v^2 \mathbf{N})}{dt} + \frac{d(\gamma \mathbf{T})}{dt} \\ &= \frac{d(v^2 \kappa)}{dt} \mathbf{N} + \frac{d\mathbf{N}}{dt} v^2 \kappa + \gamma \frac{d\mathbf{T}}{dt} + \frac{d^2 v}{dt^2} \mathbf{T} \\ &= (\gamma - \kappa^2 v^3) \mathbf{T} + \left(v^2 \frac{d\kappa}{dt} + 3\kappa \gamma v \right) \mathbf{N} + \tau \kappa v^3 \mathbf{B} \\ &= \left(\gamma - \kappa^2 v^3, v^2 \frac{d\kappa}{dt} + 3\kappa \gamma v, \tau \kappa v^3 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{B} are the tangent, normal and binormal vectors resp., and τ the *torsion* of the movement, another scalar of t . Equations 5, 6, 7 can be verified by noticing that in the case of arc length parameterization where $v = 1$, $\gamma = 0$, these become:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{ds} = \mathbf{T} = (1, 0, 0) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}}{ds^2} = \kappa \mathbf{N} = (0, \kappa, 0) \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3\mathbf{r}}{ds^3} &= \frac{d\kappa}{ds} \mathbf{N} + \kappa(\tau \mathbf{B} - \kappa \mathbf{T}) \\ &= \left(-\kappa^2, \frac{d\kappa}{ds}, \tau \kappa \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 1: A random point p on sphere \mathcal{M} , the *Frenet-Serret* frame at the current location of the particle $\alpha(t_*)$ (also denoted as point O), the vector from p to O denoted by \mathbf{r} , \mathbf{r}' the projection of \mathbf{r} on the osculating plane, ω the angle from the normal vector to \mathbf{r}' , measured on the osculating plane counterclockwise and θ the angle from the binormal to \mathbf{r} . θ is restricted to $[0, \pi]$ because the length of the projection of \mathbf{r} which equals $\|\mathbf{r}\|\sin(\theta)$ must always be positive. Angles ω and θ are scalars of time t and \mathbf{p} . \mathbf{r} is a vector also of t and \mathbf{p} .

where s is the *arc length* parameter. Equations 8, 9, 10 are standard textbook equations related to the *Frenet-Serret* frame [15].

III. THE FIRST GLOBAL KINEMATIC EQUATION

In this section, the change with time of the *total distance* $\phi(t)$ between the moving particle and all the points on the sphere will be studied. For easing out the notation, dot, double dot etc will denote first, second and respective higher derivatives with respect to t . Lets start with the distance between the particle's position and a single arbitrary point on the sphere:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|\mathbf{r}\| = \|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\| = \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} \quad (11)$$

where \cdot is the inner product. Substituting from above, $\mathbf{r} = \|\mathbf{r}\|(-\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta), \cos(\omega)\sin(\theta), -\cos(\theta))$, $\dot{\mathbf{r}} = (v(t), 0, 0)$, where $v(t)$ the speed of the moving particle, one gets:

$$\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\| = -v(t)\sin(\theta)\sin(\omega)|_{t=t_*} \quad (12)$$

hence for the *total distance* ϕ between the particle and all the

points on the sphere:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\phi}(t_*) &\equiv \left. \frac{d\phi(t)}{dt} \right|_{t=t_*} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| \\ &= \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d}{dt} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| \\ &\stackrel{12}{=} -v(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\theta)\sin(\omega)) \Big|_{t=t_*}\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

and if one denotes the integral with $C(t)$, finally gets the *first global kinematic equation* as:

$$\dot{\phi}(t_*) = -v(t_*)C(t_*) \quad (14)$$

where $C(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\theta)\sin(\omega)) \Big|_{t=t_*}$ quantifies the *angular displacement* of the sphere with respect to the position and movement of the particle at time t_* . This equation, solved for $v(t)$, defines speed in terms of an integral of distances and an integral of angles, their aggregate nature makes them resilient to noise, as summations tend to cancel out Gaussian noise.

IV. THE SECOND GLOBAL KINEMATIC EQUATION

One can proceed accordingly for the second derivative of the distance between the particle and a single arbitrary point on the sphere:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \|\mathbf{r}\| &\stackrel{11}{=} \left(\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \dot{\mathbf{r}} \right) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} \\ &= \left(\mathbf{r} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) + \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \dot{\mathbf{r}} \right) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} \\ &= -\frac{(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^3} + \frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} + \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|}\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

and substituting from Eq.1,5,6:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{r} &= \|\mathbf{r}\|(-\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta), \cos(\omega)\sin(\theta), -\cos(\theta)), \\ \dot{\mathbf{r}} &= (v, 0, 0), \\ \ddot{\mathbf{r}} &= (\gamma, \kappa v^2, 0):\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{\mathbf{r}} \Big|_{t=t_*} &= \kappa(t_*)v^2(t_*) (\cos(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\ &+ v^2(t_*) \frac{1 - \sin^2(\omega)\sin^2(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\ &- \gamma(t_*) (\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*}\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

where κ the *curvature* and γ the *acceleration* of movement, both scalars of time. Hence for the *total distance* ϕ between

the particle and all the points on the sphere:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{\phi}(t_*) &\equiv \left. \frac{d^2\phi(t)}{dt^2} \right|_{t=t_*} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| \\ &= \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| \\ &\stackrel{16}{=} \kappa(t_*)v^2(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\theta)\cos(\omega)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\ &+ v^2(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{1 - \sin^2(\omega)\sin^2(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\ &- \gamma(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\theta)\sin(\omega)) \Big|_{t=t_*}\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

and one finally gets the *second global kinematic equation* as:

$$\ddot{\phi}(t_*) = v^2(t_*)(\kappa(t_*)A(t_*) + B(t_*)) - \gamma(t_*)C(t_*) \quad (18)$$

where C as above, $A(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\theta)\cos(\omega)) \Big|_{t=t_*}$ quantifies a similar to C *angular displacement* of the sphere with respect to the position and movement of the particle at time t_* and $B(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{1 - \sin^2(\omega)\sin^2(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \Big|_{t=t_*}$ quantifies an *angular displacement* that is also relative to the *distance* of the sphere from the position of the particle at time t_* . This equation, solved for $\kappa(t)$, defines curvature in terms of an integral of distances and integrals of angles, their aggregate nature makes them resilient to noise, as already discussed before, since summations tend to cancel out Gaussian noise. $v(t)$ and its derivatives (e.g $\gamma(t)$) can be *Globally* calculated from the First Global Kinematic equation.

V. THE THIRD GLOBAL KINEMATIC EQUATION

Continuing from Eq.15 for the third derivative of the distance between the moving particle and a single point on the sphere one derives:

$$\frac{d^3}{dt^3} \|\mathbf{r}\| = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^3} \right) + \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) + \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) \quad (19)$$

Calculating separately each factor in the above summation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^3} \right) = \\
& = \frac{-2(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})\|\mathbf{r}\|^3 + 3(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})^2\|\mathbf{r}\|^2\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^6} \\
& = \frac{-2(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}})\|\mathbf{r}\|^3 + 3(\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})^2\|\mathbf{r}\|^2\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^6} \\
& \stackrel{11}{=} \frac{-2\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^2\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} - \frac{2(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}})}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} + \frac{3\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^3}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) &= \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} \\
&= \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{r}\|\ddot{\mathbf{r}} - \|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \right) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \\
&= 2\frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} - \|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\| \left(\frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right)^2 \quad (21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) &= \left(\frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \right) \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \cdot \dddot{\mathbf{r}} \\
&= \left(\frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|\mathbf{r}\| - \mathbf{r}\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \right) \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \dddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \quad (22) \\
&= \frac{\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} - \frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} + \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \dddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} \\
& \stackrel{11}{=} \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|}
\end{aligned}$$

hence from 19, 20, 21 and 22:

$$\frac{d^3}{dt^3} \|\mathbf{r}\| = \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} - \frac{3\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^2\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} + \frac{3\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\|^3}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \quad (23)$$

and substituting from Eq.1,5,6,7,12:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{r} &= \|\mathbf{r}\|(-\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta), \cos(\omega)\sin(\theta), -\cos(\theta)), \\
\dot{\mathbf{r}} &= (v, 0, 0), \\
\ddot{\mathbf{r}} &= (\gamma, \kappa v^2, 0), \\
\dddot{\mathbf{r}} &= (\gamma - \kappa^2 v^3, v^2 \frac{d\kappa}{dt} + 3\kappa\gamma v, \tau\kappa v^3), \\
\|\dot{\mathbf{r}}\| &= -v\sin(\theta)\sin(\omega):
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\ddot{\mathbf{r}}\|_{t=t_*} &= 3v^3(t_*) \frac{\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ 3v^3(t_*) \frac{\sin^3(\omega)\sin^3(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ v^2(t_*) \frac{d\kappa}{dt}(t_*) (\cos(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ 3\kappa(t_*)\gamma(t_*)v(t_*) (\cos(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&- \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dt}(t_*) - \kappa^2(t_*)v^3(t_*) \right) (\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&- \tau(t_*)\kappa(t_*)v^3(t_*) \cos(\theta) \Big|_{t=t_*} \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

where κ, γ, τ the curvature, acceleration and torsion of the movement respectively, all three scalars of time. Hence for

the total distance ϕ between the particle and all the points on the sphere:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ddot{\phi}(t_*) &\equiv \frac{d^3\phi(t)}{dt^3} \Big|_{t=t_*} = \frac{d^3}{dt^3} \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| \\
&= \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d^3}{dt^3} \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_*) - \mathbf{p}\| = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \|\ddot{\mathbf{r}}\|_{t=t_*} \\
&\stackrel{24}{=} 3v^3(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ 3v^3(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{\sin^3(\omega)\sin^3(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ v^2(t_*) \frac{d\kappa}{dt}(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\cos(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&+ 3\kappa(t_*)\gamma(t_*)v(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\cos(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&- \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dt}(t_*) - \kappa^2(t_*)v^3(t_*) \right) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} (\sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)) \Big|_{t=t_*} \\
&- \tau(t_*)\kappa(t_*)v^3(t_*) \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \cos(\theta) \Big|_{t=t_*} \quad (25)
\end{aligned}$$

one finally gets the third global kinematic equation as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ddot{\phi}(t_*) &= 3v^3(t_*)(D(t_*) + F(t_*)) \\
&+ \left(v^2(t_*) \frac{d\kappa}{dt}(t_*) + 3\kappa(t_*)\gamma(t_*)v(t_*) \right) A(t_*) \\
&- \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dt}(t_*) - \kappa^2(t_*)v^3(t_*) \right) C(t_*) \\
&- \tau(t_*)\kappa(t_*)v^3(t_*)E(t_*) \quad (26)
\end{aligned}$$

where A and C as above, $E(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \cos(\theta) \Big|_{t=t_*}$ quantifies a similat to A and C angular displacement of the sphere with respect to the position and movement of the particle at time t_* and $D(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{1 - \sin(\omega)\sin(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*}$,

$F(t_*) = \int_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{1 - \sin^3(\omega)\sin^3(\theta)}{\|\mathbf{r}\|^2} \Big|_{t=t_*}$ quantify similar to B above, angular displacements that are also relative to the square of the distance between the sphere and the position of the particle at time t_* . This equation, solved for $\tau(t)$, defines torsion in terms of an integral of distances and integrals of angles, their aggregate nature makes them resilient to noise, as already mentioned for the other kinematic equations, since summations tend to cancel out Gaussian noise. $v(t)$ and its derivatives ($\gamma(t)$ etc) can be Globally calculated from the First

Global Kinematic equation, $\kappa(t)$ and its derivatives from the second.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The robustness of the second Global Kinematic Equation (GKE) in calculating curvature is demonstrated in this experiment. For better display of motion, this experiment will be conducted in 2D but a 3D extension is straight forward. A particle then is considered moving for 100 time units, making at random instances 3 random turns at angles drawn uniformly from the ranges $[-60^\circ, -20^\circ]$ and $[20^\circ, 60^\circ]$. The particle's motion is tracked by several randomly positioned radars on the same plane. Each radar measures at each time step, its distance to the moving particle. These distance measurements are affected by Gaussian noise with varying standard deviations (0.1, 0.7, and 1.0). To estimate the particle's position, velocity, acceleration, and curvature at each time step, an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) [16] is applied using the noisy radar measurements and assuming the classic differential paradigm of motion. Curvature is estimated by EKF by means of the rest of the filter's states using the classic formula:

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{v_x(t)a_y(t) - v_y(t)a_x(t)}{(\sqrt{v_x(t)^2 + v_y(t)^2})^3} \quad (27)$$

where (v_x, v_y) the *velocity vector* and (a_x, a_y) the *acceleration vector*. The denominator thus is equivalent to the particle's *speed* raised to the third power, since *speed* is considered to signify the magnitude of the velocity vector.

EKF based curvature estimates are compared to the ones provided by the *second Global Kinematic Equation* (GKE) (18), solved for $\kappa(t)$:

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{\ddot{\phi}(t) - v^2(t)B(t) + \gamma(t)C(t)}{v^2(t)A(t)}, v(t) \neq 0, A(t) \neq 0 \quad (28)$$

In this case, radar points play the role of \mathcal{M} , thus the integrals $A(t)$, $B(t)$, $C(t)$ and $\dot{\phi}(t)$ above, are reduced to summations over all radar points calculated based on the trajectory estimated by the Extended Kalman Filter. The two methods therefore, assume the same noisy trajectory. $v(t)$ is calculated from the first Global Kinematic Equation (14) and $\gamma(t)$ from the changes of $v(t)$. It may be useful to clarify at this point that in this manuscript we are not concerned with heuristic methods of calculating curvature since the contribution lies in the *global redefinition* of the paradigm of motion and how this protects it from noise.

A comparison between equations (27) and (28) reveals some of the advantages of the Global Kinematic (GK) calculation. Indeed, the classic calculation involves directly the velocity and acceleration *vectors*, the former being tangent to the trajectory thus directly affected by noise, a detrimental effect that is only amplified in the acceleration vector. One thus expects this calculation of curvature to be severely affected by noise, a fact that will be verified by the experiments. The Global Kinematic calculation on the other hand, involves only the *magnitude* of the velocity vector (speed) and the magnitude of the *tangential component* of

the accelerator vector (γ). The other terms are integrals (or summations) that are not affected significantly by noise, one thus expects this calculation of curvature to be more resisting to noise, a fact also verified by the experiments that follow.

The comparison is performed by means of the mean point-wise absolute error between each method and the ground truth. The ground-truth considers only three high curvature points when the particle take sudden turns as was explained above. The mean error for each method is shown in the comparison image. In the following figures, starting with Fig.(2), odd rows hold random trajectories as these were estimated by the Extended Kalman Filter using radar distances for varying Gaussian noise, the standard deviation of which is shown in the legends of this row. Radar locations are also shown as blue dots. The image just below each trajectory holds the performance comparison between Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and Global Kinematic (GK) methods in estimating the curvature of the movement at each time step. Both methods were initially tested without noise and were accurate in their curvature estimations. As noise increases to a standard deviation (std) of 0.1 both methods exhibit similar performance degradation. At noise levels between 0.7 and 1.0 standard deviations, EKF collapses in the sense that it localizes noise as high curvature points thus identifies vertices almost everywhere and its performance degrades rapidly. GK on the other hand exhibits better resistance to noise since global descriptors are less affected by local perturbations as was explained in the conceptual comparison of the actual equations above.

VII. EPILOGUE

The *Global Kinematic Equations* presented in this manuscript attempt to redefine the differential parameters of motion in a way that noise is not affecting them severely thus more suitable for practical applications. The scenario of multiple radars tracking a moving particle with noisy distance measurements, examined in the experiments, reveal that even the Extended Kalman Filter collapses in its estimation of curvature in the presence of increased noise (e.g jamming). Measurements based on the Global Kinematic Equations, on the other hand, exhibit high resistance to noise. At least for this reason, their inception has been justified.

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Fig. 2: Odd rows hold various random trajectories, estimated by means of an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) from noisy distance measurements from a varying number of randomly placed radars. Radars are shown as blue dots and vary in numbers and locations. The standard deviation of the noise applied to all radar distances is also shown in the image. The image just below each trajectory holds curvature estimations achieved by the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and the second Global Kinematic Equation (18), together with the ground truth where only three vertices (turns) are considered. The comparison is performed by means of mean absolute error and is shown in the image together with the location and magnitude (as the angle of turn) of ground truth vertices (turns). See text for details and a discussion on the results.

Fig. 3: Same caption as in Fig.(2).

Fig. 4: Same caption as in Fig.(2).

Fig. 5: Same caption as in Fig.(2).

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